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Promising directions for the development of Russian civil aircraft in the context of sanctions pressure

KEYWORDS

aviation industry,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The sanctions imposed against the Russian Federation limited access to foreign components and technologies, which jeopardized the production and maintenance of Russia's civil aviation. Under the conditions of sanctions, the development of domestic output for components and equipment in the aircraft industry is becoming a key factor in ensuring the industry's independence.

This article aims to investigate the specifics of the Russian aviation industry's development under sanctions, identify the main problems, and assess the industry's prospects.

Materials and methods. The research materials were official documents and reports, including strategies for the development of the aviation industry, as well as reports from the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Russian Federation and other government agencies. The methods employed included data analysis and SWOT analysis.

Results. Western sanctions against Russian airlines have caused significant damage to the country, but at the same time, they have become a serious incentive for the development of the domestic aviation industry. Despite the sanctions war, the Russian aviation industry is continuing to develop dynamically. The government approved an industry development program, under which the share of domestic aircraft in the Russian airline fleet is expected to grow from the current 33% to 81% by 2030. In total, during this time, it is planned to supply carriers with 1,036 aircraft. The total budget of the program exceeds 400 billion rubles.

Conclusion. The success of developing the domestic aviation industry depends on the state's efforts, as almost all production and design capacities are concentrated in its hands. Finding alternative suppliers and creating their technologies for component and equipment production can reduce dependence on imports and strengthen the industry's independence. It is essential to foster cooperation with countries that do not support sanctions, thereby opening up new markets and sources of financing, as well as promoting the exchange of technologies and expertise.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that the sanctions imposed against the Russian Federation limited access to foreign components and technologies, which jeopardized the production and maintenance of civil aviation in Russia. Under the conditions of sanctions, the development of domestic output for components and equipment in the aircraft industry is becoming a key factor in ensuring the industry's independence. The search for new sales markets and the development of promising aircraft models that will help preserve competencies and ensure the loading of enterprises are also relevant.

Developing new aircraft models that meet modern safety and environmental standards, while enhancing their competitiveness in the global market, is a crucial task for ensuring the sustainable development of the industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

E. B. Lenchuk analyzes the impact of sanctions on the development of high-tech sectors of the Russian economy, their current consequences for the economy, and possible risks in the future, while also assessing the effectiveness of anti-sanction measures in this area. The authors presented proposals on the main directions of state policy aiming to overcome technological dependence, accelerate technological modernization in Russia, and mobilize scientific and technological potential for the development and implementation of key breakthrough technologies [1].

L. Sobolev analyzes the labor productivity and competitiveness of Russian aviation companies, drawing on the experience of successful Western companies, as well as trends and forecasts for the development of the global aviation industry. According to the author, the gap in labor productivity between the Russian aviation industry and Western aerospace corporations is increasing, despite significant state investments in the industry, the introduction of information technologies, and the technical re-equipment of major industries. The primary obstacles to labor productivity growth in the Russian aviation industry are monopolization, weak management, and a lack of motivation for productive work [2].

A. N. Klepach et al. propose an approach to a comprehensive assessment of Russia's scientific and technical activity in comparison with that of leading foreign countries. An analysis of the existing imbalances in the development of the scientific

and technical sphere in Russia, along with the reasons for the failure to fulfill many strategic goals, was conducted. A forecast of scientific and technical development was made under the existing management system, assessing the potential impact and cost of measures aimed at increasing Russia's technological sovereignty and forming an advanced knowledge economy [3].

M. Yevtodyeva and I. Danilin analyze the dynamics of internationalization in the Russian aircraft industry over the past decade (2008-2017) in two periods: before and after the introduction of economic sanctions against the Russian Federation in 2014. The authors consider key elements of international cooperation in the civil aviation industry, including cooperation with foreign suppliers of parts and components, export supplies to foreign airlines, research and development (R&D) collaboration, sales, and after-sales service. The authors conclude that the structure of investment in the aviation industry still retains a high share of targeted government funding, while the share of foreign direct investment has been declining in recent years. According to the authors, the development of the Russian civil aircraft industry can be ensured in the context of Western sanctions by forming effective business strategies that increase the efficiency of financing mechanisms, stimulate sales, and enhance after-sales service [4].

E. Stepanov et al. analyze export strategies of Russian civil aviation enterprises based on annual reports of enterprises and ratings of Russian analytical agencies. The authors identify the peculiarities of foreign economic activity and export strategies of Russian corporations of the transport engineering complex [5].

J. Kovalchuk examines the impact of suspending passenger aircraft flights during a pandemic on the formation of stability trajectories, as well as strategies for diversifying aviation company activities. The author presents an assessment of the development strategy of Russian airlines, including modeling of possible trajectories for a gradual increase in the number of flights as borders open, domestic tourism develops, and vaccinations are carried out worldwide [6].

N. M. Tyukavkin et al. consider the problem of program-targeted state financing of programs for the development of aircraft. The authors point out that the current state of the Russian economy, characterized by the lack of a competitive management system at aircraft manufacturing enterprises, leads to dependence on imports, which significantly affects the country's security, therefore, it is necessary to assess the effectiveness of state financing of targeted aircraft construction programs based on the calculation project indicators [7].

A. N. Vasil'tsova, based on an analysis of materials from 1,700 companies, classifies the enterprises of the Russian aviation industry and identifies their production links. The authors reveal the territorial structure of production ties between aircraft manufacturing enterprises, which has a pronounced centripetal character: three-fifths of all ties are with the Moscow capital region. Based on the analysis of the location of enterprises and the structure of their ties, the aviation industry is zoned. The specialization and characteristic features of the territorial structure of each of the ten regions is determined: the capital region specializes in R&D, the Western region – in avionics and repairs, the Black Earth region – in avionics and aircraft assembly, the Southern, Volga, Baikal and Far Eastern regions – in the assembly of aircraft and helicopters, Northern and Priobsky – on components and engines, Ural – on materials, parts and engines [8].

A. Vasilcova demonstrates that if the aviation industry of Siberia and the Far East holds a dominant position in the region's mechanical engineering and even determines its specialization, then in the old industrial regions of the Middle Volga region, the aircraft industry is organically integrated into the developed industrial environment. A "compression" of aircraft manufacturing space is revealed, where mass production is concentrated in single centers, and aircraft manufacturing is being withdrawn from non-Russian territories of the post-Soviet space. The author establishes an "eastern" gradient in the placement of new production sites: in the post-Soviet period, they developed in the Siberian and Far Eastern regions [9].

N. A. Serova & V. A. Serova write that the tasks of large-scale development of Arctic resources are inextricably linked with the need to develop and modernize transport infrastructure. The authors demonstrate that objective difficulties and high risks to transport functioning in Arctic regions are caused not only by unfavorable natural and geographical conditions but also by systematic underfunding of the transport industry as a whole [10].

I. Poleshkina identifies reasons that prevent the use of existing methods for assessing transport accessibility in the territories of the Arctic zone. Such reasons include a lack of railway communication, a lack of year-round roads, the high cost of passenger intraregional air transportation, low regularity of flights, and a limited regular network of existing airlines [11].

Several authors highlight the role of information technologies in enhancing the efficiency, safety, reliability, and environmental sustainability of the civil aircraft industry, thereby reducing development time and costs.

N. K. Chaika analyses factors such as aircraft lifetime costs, direct operating costs, maintenance, and repair costs. The role of information technologies at the present stage of aircraft model of interaction between participants in the aircraft life cycle is considered. Constant iterative processes of information exchange between manufacturers, operators, and authorities form complex requirements for the production of competitive aircraft [12].

M. A. Fedotova et al. consider areas of innovative development in the aviation industry enterprises. In this regard, the historical development of the Russian aviation industry, the specifics of the projects implemented within it, digitalization, and the modern aspects of innovation introduction are considered, as well as state regulation, strategic importance, the interplay between civil and military developments, and the role of intersectoral interaction. The authors highlight the peculiarities of developing and implementing civil and military projects [13].

K.P. Tairov analyzes the prospects for interaction between Russia's civil aviation industry and its military aviation industry. The author concludes that ultrafast changes in socio-economic processes, particularly in the context of sanctions, can lead to an uncontrolled increase in destabilizing factors in the civil and military aviation industries. The military sector of the military-industrial complex will have a significant synergistic effect on the development of the military aviation industry and the entire domestic aviation industry in Russia. It will address the issues related to the continuity of knowledge transfer, particularly in the context of serial production of military aircraft [14].

D. Ivanov et al. focus on the technological prospects of the aviation industry. The authors discuss how the introduction of advanced technologies can address the primary challenges currently facing the industry, including high maintenance and refueling costs, as well as environmental pollution. One of the most promising technologies for autonomous piloting of aircraft is analyzed, and potential areas of its application are investigated [15].

D. A. Zatuchny et al. develop methods and algorithms for enhancing the noise immunity of navigation systems used by civil aviation aircraft operating based on satellite radio navigation systems, as well as improving the quality of transmitting navigation information by selecting a rational communication resource [16].

A. Stepanenko et al. consider the aspects of introducing digital products into the technological processes of organizing air transportation, as well as

the specifics of these processes. The authors determine the values of the criterion for the effectiveness of digital products within the general system of transportation organization [17].

E. Pronina and M. Rodionov consider the problem of creating a measuring mechanism for quantifying the effectiveness of airline business processes. The authors proposed mathematical models for indicators of reliability, performance, and cost-effectiveness of the business process, as well as approaches to building an integrated performance indicator [18].

The authors also focus on enhancing the personnel training system, which is a crucial component of theoretical and applied research aimed at improving the efficiency of the air transport operation process [19]. Innovative components that implement a model-oriented approach in the sectoral education system are associated with the implementation of measures to restructure the educational cluster of civil aviation [20]. The development of conceptual foundations for a model approach to improving the training system for airlines enables us to address a number of problem-oriented issues related to industry staffing [21].

Analysis of sources reveals the importance of studying and analyzing existing theories and models of the aviation industry's development, their adaptation to the conditions of sanctions pressure, and the specifics of the Russian market. To understand the current state and prospects for the development of the Russian civil aircraft industry, it is necessary to conduct empirical research and collect and analyze data on production, exports, imports, investments, and other relevant indicators. Based on an analysis of existing data, it is necessary to develop new approaches and models that describe the prospects for the development of the Russian civil aircraft industry under sanctions.

The analysis shows that many authors believe that, despite the sanctions restrictions, the Russian civil aircraft industry in the future has the potential to focus on creating an entirely domestic technological base, increasing the localization of production and developing innovative solutions to ensure competitiveness in the domestic market and, in the future, in the international arena.

Sanction pressure on the aviation sector brought many problems to Russia. The situation is further aggravated by the fact that domestic air transport is mainly dependent on Western countries: European and American-made aircraft predominate in airline fleets, and the civilian aircraft industry has experienced a significant decline in the decades since the collapse of the Soviet Union.

In recent years, comprehensive measures are taken in Russia to revive the aircraft industry. Various types of aircraft are being developed and modernized, and significant funds are being invested in organizing and expanding production. Nevertheless, there are problems in this area, and against the backdrop of the escalating sanctions crisis, a multiple acceleration of the processes reviving the aviation industry is required.

The purpose of this article is to investigate the specifics of the Russian aviation industry's development under sanctions, identify the main problems, and assess the industry's prospects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials consisted of official documents and reports, including strategies for the development of the aviation industry, as well as reports from the Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Russian Federation and other government agencies, and also statistics from government agencies and industry associations, publications in the media and peer-reviewed periodical scientific journals (Studies on Russian Economic Development, Economic Analysis: Theory and Practice, World Economy and International Relations, Russian Engineering Research, Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, Russian Economic Bulletin, Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, and others).

Methods: data analysis (methods of descriptive statistics), SWOT analysis (assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the Russian civil aircraft industry, as well as the possibilities and threats associated with sanctions pressure).

RESULTS

1. Sanction pressure on the Russian passenger air transportation market as an incentive for the development of domestic civil aviation

In light of the significant crises caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the imposition of sanctions, it is necessary to examine the current state of Russian civil aviation. The article by A. A. O. Dunyamaliev highlights the proposed state measures of support and interaction aimed at ensuring the stability and development of this industry, while also considering potential strategies and prospects for the development of aviation enterprises in the face of current challenges [22]. I. V. Bazikova wrote about the state and prospects for the development of Russian exports of civil aviation

equipment [23]. M. V. Karpova et al. highlight the transformation of the aviation industry in the context of sanctions against Russia since 2014, as well as a new wave of restrictions in 2022, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on its functioning [24]. A. A. Bychkova was engaged in simulating the risks of air transport as a result of the impact of sanctions restrictions on Russia [25].

The sanctions imposed by unfriendly countries on the Russian civil aviation sector are complex [26]. After the start of a special military operation in Ukraine, the United States and its European satellites imposed a ban on the supply of aircraft to Russian carriers. Lessors who owned foreign aircraft put forward demands for the return of their assets. As a result, our country has lost seventy-six passenger aircraft [27]. Russia has attempted to reach agreements with lessors, but these efforts have been unsuccessful.

Most Russian aircraft were registered abroad, mainly in Bermuda and Ireland. Control of the state of aviation equipment was also carried out in these countries. Following the imposition of sanctions in 2022, the registrars suspended the validity of airworthiness certificates for Russian aircraft, arguing that under the new conditions, they cannot fully monitor the condition of the aircraft to ensure flight safety.

In response, Russia froze agreements with Bermuda to control the condition of aircraft and assigned this function to the Federal Air Transport Agency. Additionally, a regulatory framework was established for the transfer of aircraft to the national register [28].

After the United States and European countries introduced bans on Russian aircraft flights over their territories, the number of open foreign routes for domestic airlines decreased significantly. Russian carriers began to use some of the released aircraft as donors of spare parts. This made it possible to achieve a certain time lag for a systematic solution to the problem of supplying repair capacities with spare parts through the use of parallel import mechanisms via friendly and neutral countries (such as China, India, and EAEU countries), as well as through in-house production.

Notably, many Russian companies specializing in aircraft repair, as well as the corresponding divisions of airlines, have a substantial production base, which was established during Soviet times and subsequently modernized. It is possible to produce a wide range of spare parts for American and European aircraft, and currently, work is underway to expand production capabilities [29]. At the same time, the experience of countries that already found themselves in a similar situation, in particular Iran, is being actively adopted.

In recent decades, Russia became increasingly dependent on the supply of foreign aircraft and their spare parts. For example, between 2015 and 2020, domestic air carriers purchased approximately 600 foreign aircraft and around 50 Russian ones. These foreign aircraft account for nearly 93% of the country's passenger air traffic. At the same time, Boeing and Airbus occupy about 60% of the Russian market. Ships of these manufacturers, in particular, form the basis of the fleets of the largest Russian carriers: Aeroflot, S7, and UTair, which dominate medium- to long-haul flights [29]. Also on the domestic market are Bombardier (Canada), Embraer (Brazil), and ATR (a joint venture between Italy and France) aircraft. The only airline operating domestic flights on vessels (SSJ-100 and Tu-204) is Red Wings [30].

According to statistics from the Transport Strategy of the Russian Federation [31], in 2022, approximately 1,300 aircraft and 2,270 helicopters were in operation at domestic air carriers. Among them, foreign-made aircraft accounted for 824 units (64%), and helicopters for 1,459 thousand (36%).

The strategy states that by 2030, Russian air carriers will require approximately 700 new aircraft and 438 helicopters. The authors' forecasts are based on data regarding potential traffic growth, as well as the need to replace more than 800 foreign-made aircraft that will be decommissioned due to wear and tear. To provide companies with aircraft, it is planned to form a competitive offer of Russian-made trunk and regional ships.

2. The work of the Russian civil aviation industry under sanctions: the current situation and problems

The sanctions imposed by Western countries against Russian airlines caused significant damage to our country. Still, at the same time, they are a serious incentive for the development of the domestic aviation industry. Solving the problems will require a significant amount of time and investment. However, Russia has the necessary groundwork to restore the aircraft industry and ensure the safe transportation of passengers and goods in the required volume.

The United States and its satellites imposed sanctions not only against Russian air carriers but also against companies in the aviation industry. In particular, the sanctions lists included: Rostec and its members United Aircraft Corporation (UAC), United Engine Corporation (UEC), Irkut (Yakovlev), Russian Helicopters, and Sukhoi. These companies are prohibited from attracting capital in Western financial markets, as well as purchasing equipment and components in the United States and the European Union.

Sanctions pressure on the Russian aviation industry began after 2014 (the annexation of Crimea to the Russian Federation). In 2018, the United States imposed sanctions against Aerocomposite, which produces a composite wing for the MS-21 aircraft, causing a two-year delay in certification of the liner (this time was required for import substitution) [32]. After February 2022, sectional pressure on the Russian aviation industry became systemic.

The sanctions caused severe damage to the Russian aviation industry, given its deep international cooperation. This was especially evident in the production of the regional liner, the Sukhoi Superjet-100 (SSJ-100). Components for this aircraft were supplied by Liebherr (Germany), Thales (France), Honeywell, and Hamilton Sundstrand (the United States). Engines for the airliner (SaM146) were produced in Rybinsk at the joint venture Safran-PowerJet (France) and UEC Saturn [33].

In the spring of 2022, Safran-PowerJet stopped supplying components for the engine and refused to provide technical support and repairs. Under the current conditions, this function is assigned to UEC-Saturn. In recent years, a substantial stock of spare parts has been accumulated, enabling you to service the SSJ-100 for an extended period.

Date, an import-substituted version of the Sukhoi Superjet (SJ-100) aircraft, which is equipped with domestic PD-8 engines, avionics, and other systems. The plans for the coming years are to release this version exclusively. Production is carried out at the aircraft plant in Komsomolsk-on-Amur.

A significant role in import substitution in civil aviation should be played by a medium-haul airliner, the MS-21, with a capacity of 163 to 211 passengers. It was based on Soviet developments (Yak-242). This aircraft is produced in Irkutsk [34]. Preparations are currently underway for serial production.

It will take some time for the MS-21 to enter mass production on a large scale. Therefore, in the coming years, the problem of the shortage of medium-haul aircraft is planned to be addressed through the production of the Tu-214 (with a capacity of up to 210 passengers). This liner is produced at the Kazan aircraft plant. The Tu-214 is a modification of the classic Tu-204 model, developed in the late 1980s to replace the obsolete Tu-154. It was also produced in Kazan (1996).

Tu-204 is used mainly by state special customers (special flight detachment "Russia", special services). However, several copies are used on regular flights in the

fleets of Russian airlines, for example, Red Wings. They were also previously purchased by Transaero. This aircraft, in its technical, operational, and economic parameters, is comparable to the Airbus A321 and Boeing 757. The Tu-204 did not enter mass production at one time, which was attributed to the domestic airlines' preference for purchasing imported aircraft, as well as the priority given to the Sukhoi Superjet project. According to the United Aircraft Corporation, the Tu-214 is equipped with entirely Russian systems and is not dependent on imports. The aircraft meets high-quality and safety standards [35].

Notably, during the first decade of the UAC's existence, the IL-96-300 and Tu-334 projects were put on hold – currently, only the SSJ-100 remains. The IL-96-300 is produced in single copies, despite the UAC leadership's official announcement in 2015 to mass-produce this aircraft. Nevertheless, at the moment, these airliners are only in operation at the SLO Rossiya (11 aircraft) and the Cuban airline Cubana de Aviación (3 jets). For some time, one IL-96-300 was used on Aeroflot flights but was subsequently decommissioned [36].

Noteworthy is the joint Russian-Chinese project for the development and production of the wide-body, long-range airliner, the CR929. However, this project is long-term (planned for implementation by 2045) and is currently not a priority for the domestic aviation industry. It should also be noted that this project was scheduled to be implemented in close cooperation with Western manufacturers of components. In particular, it was intended to install Rolls-Royce or General Electric engines on the CR929 [37].

Currently, mass production of the regional aircraft IL 114-300 is being prepared. According to its technical characteristics, it will not be able to replace the SJ-100 fully, but it has.

3. Industry Outlook

Despite the sanctions war, the Russian aviation industry is continuing to develop dynamically. The government has approved an industry development program, under which the share of domestic aircraft in the Russian airline fleet is expected to grow from the current 33% to 81% by 2030. In total, it is planned to deliver 1,036 aircraft to carriers during this time (see Table 1) [33]. The total budget of the program exceeds 400 billion rubles.

Table 1

Actual and forecast data on domestic aircraft deliveries to Russian airlines

Aircraft type	Capacity, people	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	Total units
SSJ-NEW (SJ-100)	98-103	-	2	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	142
MS-21-310	181 – 211	-	-	6	12	22	36	50	72	72	270
IL-114-300	64 – 68	-	-	2	8	12	12	12	12	12	70
Tu-214	150 – 215	-	3	7	10	10	10	10	10	10	70
IL-96-300	237 – 300	-	-	-	2	2	2	2	2	2	12
TVRS-44 Ladoga	44	-	-	-	15	25	25	25	25	25	140
L-410	15-19	18	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	178
Baikal (LMS-901)	9	-	-	14	15	25	25	25	25	25	154
Total	-	15	25	69	102	136	150	164	186	186	1036

The geopolitical confrontation with the West has necessitated adjustments to Russia's plans for the MS-21. Initially, it was planned to equip this aircraft with both Russian PD-14 engines and American Pratt & Whitney engines. UAC intends to deliver the first batch of four liners with foreign engines by early 2023. The buyer is Rossiya Airlines. Due to the changed circumstances, the production dates of the first batch were shifted to 2024. According to current plans, all MS-21 aircraft will be equipped with Russian engines [38].

The Parallel production of several aircraft models (SJ-100, MS-21, Tu-214, IL-114) in conditions of broad production cooperation will allow for diversifying risks and achieving the necessary production rhythm in the segment of short- and medium-haul liners. The need for wide-body long-haul aircraft will likely lead to the closure of IL-96-300 production. The needs of regional aviation will be met by the mass production of the L-410, also known as the Ladoga or Baikal, aircraft.

The largest Russian air carrier, Aeroflot, is expected to receive 18 MS-21 airliners, 34 SJ-100, and 11 Tu-214 in 2024 [39]. In total, until 2030, Aeroflot plans to supply 339 domestic airliners. Procurement plans include 210 MS-21, 89 SSJ-NEW, and 40 Tu-214. The total value of the contracts exceeds 1 trillion. Rubles.

Before the imposition of sanctions, Aeroflot planned to expand its fleet mainly through imported aircraft. As of 31.01.2024, the fleet of Aeroflot Group (including Aeroflot, Russia, and Pobeda) totaled 349 aircraft, including 59 wide-body, 212 narrow-body medium-haul (manufactured by Airbus and Boeing), as well as 78 domestic regional Superjet 100 [40].

Plans for the order of domestic equipment, particularly the MS-21, have one of the largest Russian carriers, S7, whose fleet currently consists exclusively of foreign liners. However, these plans are focused on the long term.

Thus, in the coming years, the Russian aviation industry plans to supply domestic carriers with high-quality, reliable, and cost-effective aircraft in the required volumes. The country has the necessary scientific, technical, personnel, and production base, and there is every reason to expect that the planned plans will be generally fulfilled. Although given the experience, some time shifts are possible. Nevertheless, in the current circumstances, the aircraft building complex must provide the country with domestically built aircraft and thereby make a significant contribution to the country's transport and economic security.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study showed that Western pressure had a profound impact on the Russian air transportation sector, as well as on the civilian aircraft industry. Nevertheless, our country as a whole was prepared for such a development of events and is currently conducting systematic work to revive the aviation industry, introducing advanced developments and establishing mass production of a wide range of civilian aircraft.

The success of the domestic aviation industry's development depends mainly on the state's efforts, as almost all production and design capacities are concentrated in its hands. Additionally, effective measures are necessary to influence the air transportation industry to balance supply and demand for aircraft. International production cooperation, friendly and neutral countries play a significant role. The task of bringing the domestic aviation industry to maximum capacity is challenging and requires the involvement of substantial financial and material resources. The industry must be provided with qualified personnel. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the training of young specialists in secondary and higher educational institutions, as well as directly at enterprises. To train specialists in the workplace, it is necessary to develop the institution of mentoring actively.

Generally, the sanctions provided impetus to the development of the Russian aviation industry, which had seriously declined in recent decades. Given that the sanctions war is unlikely to end in the near future, domestic companies will be compelled to purchase Russian-made aircraft. The main task in this case is to ensure the production of high-quality, comfortable, and safe aircraft in the required volumes

and nomenclature. The establishment of mass production and the construction of service networks focused on servicing domestic aircraft will significantly reduce transportation costs and thereby increase the economic efficiency of air transport use. The aviation industry is strategically important for our country. Therefore, the issue of its development is a national security priority.

Finding alternative suppliers and developing our technologies for component and equipment production can reduce dependence on imports and strengthen the industry's independence. It is essential to foster cooperation with countries that do not support sanctions, thereby opening up new markets and sources of financing, as well as promoting the exchange of technologies and expertise. The development of educational programs and cooperation with leading technical universities can contribute to the training of qualified specialists and engineers necessary for the industry's development. The introduction of digital technologies into production processes can increase their efficiency and competitiveness, as well as open up new opportunities for optimization and innovation.

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